

COLLABORATIVE AND PROJECT-BASED LEARNING IN FINE ARTS

T. Marín García¹P. Marín García²¹ Universidad Miguel Hernández, Facultad de Bellas Artes de Aitea (SPAIN)² University of Cambridge, Spanish and Portuguese Department (UNITED KINGDOM)

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Abstract:

This paper deals with a Collaborative learning based on projects experience which took place, during one semester (academic year 2010-11), in the School of Fine Arts (Universidad Miguel Hernández-UMH).

In this experience we develop an innovative approach in the learning of Fine Arts. We introduce collaborative methodologies, we link projects to real situations and places, and we used a blended learning environment in which a combination of actions in class and virtual tools were used. With regard to virtual tools, some Google applications were used, within the framework of an innovative teaching project linked to the GoUMH agreement between UMH and Google

Main aims of this experience were: to experiment on tools and methodologies that allowed the development of active processes of learning by the students, together with the acquisition of digital competences and team work skills for the development of artistic projects in real contexts; b) to assess the usefulness, difficulties and satisfaction levels of these methodologies and learning environments from both students and lecturer point of view; c) to check the viability of these methodologies and learning environments as practical mechanisms to facilitate the progressive adaptation of Fine Arts degree to the requirements of the new degree curriculum (European Higher Education Area).

Site of the experience: <https://sites.google.com/a/goumh.umh.es/laboratorio-de-estrategias-creativas/inicio>

Keywords:

Project-Based Learning(PBL), Collaborative Learning, Fine Arts, Blended Learning, Web 2.0.